
**REPRODUCING "REEVALUATING THE
CHANGE POINT DETECTION PROBLEM
WITH SEGMENT-BASED BAYESIAN
ONLINE DETECTION"**

**Group 03-B, Group Assignment Experiment
Design in Data Science WS 2023/2024**

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1 Introduction

Change point detection is commonly used to identify transitions between stages of data creation within a time series. Current change point detection methods presume instantaneous transitions and focus on identifying a single point of data to categorize. However, this assumption is erroneous as many time series show quick changes between data creation phases. Previous researches indicate that Bayesian Online Change Point Detection (BOCPD) [1] is the most effective method for detecting change points across various time series. This work investigates modifying it by implementing a segment-based mechanism, with the idea of finding segments of abrupt changes within a time series.

2 Paper Description

The new proposed method experimented with, Segment-based Bayesian Online Detection (SB-BOCPD) [2], evaluates a narrow window of recent data from a stream, rather than a single point. After, identifying sudden changes in the time series, the window is compared to probability density functions calculated from preceding data in the stream.

The paper tests SB-BOCPD on a data set consisting of 31 real-world time series and 5 artificially generated time series, that were created from a survey article that collected time series from many domains and used different human annotators to designate change points. The authors used two conventional measures, covering and F1-score, to evaluate CPD annotations from numerous sources.

This paper's contributions are summarized below:

- The study is the first to investigate recognizing sudden shifts in a time series as a short portion, rather than a single point.
- They developed Segment-Based Bayesian Online Detection (SB-BOCPD), a change detection system that combines Bayesian change point detection with a segment-based mechanism to identify sudden changes within a limited timeframe.
- Their suggested technique was then validated using 36 time-series data points and two standard metrics of evaluation.

3 Paper Methodology

The SB-BOCPD algorithm was evaluated using covering and F_1 score, two widely used metrics, increasing comparability. Also the 36 used datasets were diverse and chosen from a benchmark paper, making the results even more comparable. Sadly some of the Datasets were unavailable for us at the point of writing, as described in chapter 4.2.

We had a concern with the methodology regarding the missing splitting into test and train data. It is important to split data into a train and a test set, possibly even a tune or validate set are needed. This is common practice, see for example [3]. There is no mention of if this splitting is done. In the code shared on GitHub no splitting is done. Although the code might not have been used for the final evaluation. If it was not done and the model

is trained and tested on the whole dataset, information from the test set directly influences model behaviour, leading to overfitting in the final result. Although there is no learning as an Artificial Neural Network would do, there is still hyper-parameter search, which could significantly change the algorithm’s behavior. This can and does cause over-fitting [3].

Assuming that splitting was done, there is no mention of how the data was split, not the sizes nor the algorithm and seeding, therefore reproducing this split is impossible, making the results shown in the paper irreproducible.

4 Reproduction

During our research, we found a source code and the test sequence they used for their paper. The source code also contained information about the datasets they were using and link to the repository with them.

For this particular task, we decided to follow the PRIMAD Model and test out the code in different approaches. However, due to the lack of code for the BOCPD method they are using to compare the result, we are quite limited in the list of different test types we can apply to it. In particular, we tested the code with:

- Repetition
- Parameters sweep
- On different platforms
- Actor independence

4.1 Helpful information

The research paper included many insights and explanations that were all helpful in analyzing their experiment and evaluating our results.

Metrics measurements In the experiment of the research paper, only 2 standard measurements were used for evaluation, but it was explained in the paper that these metrics are the frequently used techniques in the field. The author also referred to other recent studies using the same evaluation measurements, confirming that these values provide relevant information.

Deterministic model The steps of the algorithm were easily reproducible in the sense, that it did not contain any randomness, and no random seed or random generator was implemented. Also, the algorithm was not dependent on the data, we also experimented with other inputs, for example, using other time-series data had the deterministic result that was expected.

4.2 Problems faced

During the reproduction, our team faced a few problems regarding the specification of the project and the source code we had.

Version control Unfortunately, the authors didn't explicitly specify the software, platform, and hardware requirements for the project. So the version of Python and libraries are unknown and caused some minor issues with numpy functions.

Dataset missing Some datasets are removed from the original repository and are used for testing. Some of the datasets they are using special scraping code with turned out to be outdated and thus we couldn't retrieve all datasets they used in the paper.

Ethical issues Although a website link was provided to access the datasets [4], the third-party data repository was not documented efficiently. There was no information about the source of the data nor the environmental specifics of the data collection process. The lack of complete documentation was not just an inconvenient issue for reproducibility, e.g. we do not know the actual meaning of a data column, but also an ethical issue. Since the data collection is not published, we could violate any ethical guidelines, personal privacy, or intellectual property rights.

Code incompleteness The original code contained numerous minor mistakes. In particular, the dataset iteration loop was built incorrectly, and indexes were combined using an outdated numpy array aggregation function that cannot be used anymore. In addition, the code output was generating a huge amount of plots and in-between metrics that were irrelevant to the original metrics and were simply redundant.

Missing environmental setup The author published in the research paper that the code has a linear space- and time complexity, but it was not mentioned how much time the code execution takes. The paper lacks any information regarding the environmental setup employed during the experiments. The complete absence of detailed documentation on the software, and especially the hardware configurations limited the ability to recreate the experimental conditions accurately because we did not know if we had the necessary resources for implementation.

dataset	status
apple	Excluded form original paper evaluation.
bank	Present and tested.
bec_waggle_6	Excluded form original paper evaluation.
bitcoin	Dataset is unavailable in data repository.
brent_spot	Present and tested.
businv	Present and tested.
centralia	Dataset is unavailable in data repository.
children_per_woman	Present and tested.
co2.canada	Present and tested.
construction	Present and tested.
debt_ireland	Present and tested.
gdp_argentina	Present and tested.
gdp_croatia	Present and tested.
gdp_iran	Present and tested.
gdp_japan	Present and tested.
global_co2	Present and tested.
homeruns	Present and tested.
iceland_tourism	Excluded form original paper evaluation.
jfk_passengers	Present and tested.
lga_passengers	Present and tested.
mesles	Dataset is unavailable in data repository.
nile	Present and tested.
occupancy	Excluded form original paper evaluation.
ozone	Present and tested.
quality_control1	Present and tested.
quality_control2	Present and tested.
quality_control3	Present and tested.
quality_control4	Present and tested.
quality_control5	Present and tested.
rail_lines	Present and tested.
ratner_stock	Dataset is unavailable in data repository.
robocalls	Dataset is unavailable in data repository.
run_log	Excluded form original paper evaluation.
scanline_126007	Dataset is unavailable in data repository.
scanline_42049	Dataset is unavailable in data repository.
seatbelts	Present and tested.
shanghai_license	Present and tested.
uk_coal_employ	Present and tested.
unemployment_nl	Present and tested.
usd_isk	Present and tested.
us_population	Present and tested.
well_log	Present and tested.

Figure 1: Dataset status

No community engagement We did a short research, looking for discussions or feedback from the expert community regarding the reproducibility of the work, but could not find any critiques or comments for clarifications. Also, the four research papers that cited this paper did not provide relevant feedback that could have been helpful.

4.3 Reproduction process

For reproduction, we collected available datasets and modified the existing code to be able to get the results.

As a result, we achieved the same metrics for datasets that were available as in the original paper.

4.4 Reproduction results

Dataset	F ₁ -Score		Covering Score	
	BOCPD	SB-BOCPD	BOCPD	SB-BOCPD
bank	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
bitcoin	0.733	0.615	0.822	0.782
brent_spot	0.609	0.597	0.667	0.652
businv	0.588	0.776	0.693	0.696
centralia	1.000	0.909	0.753	0.675
children_per_woman	0.712	0.810	0.801	0.861
co2_canada	0.924	0.679	0.773	0.631
construction	0.709	0.750	0.585	0.679
debt_ireland	1.000	0.958	0.688	0.814
gdp_argentina	0.947	0.889	0.737	0.737
gdp_croatia	1.000	1.000	0.708	0.833
gdp_iran	0.862	1.000	0.583	0.814
gdp_japan	1.000	1.000	0.802	0.802
global_co2	0.889	0.929	0.758	0.758
homeruns	0.829	0.879	0.694	0.694
jfk_passengers	0.776	0.966	0.837	0.873
lga_passengers	0.704	0.683	0.547	0.596
measles	0.947	0.947	0.951	0.951
nile	1.000	1.000	0.888	0.857
ozone	0.857	1.000	0.602	0.852
quality_control_1	1.000	1.000	0.996	0.989
quality_control_2	1.000	1.000	0.927	0.917
quality_control_3	1.000	1.000	0.997	0.997
quality_control_4	0.787	0.780	0.673	0.673
quality_control_5	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
rail_lines	0.966	0.966	0.768	0.872
rairner_stock	0.868	0.889	0.906	0.874
robocalls	0.966	1.000	0.808	0.752
scanline_126007	0.921	0.748	0.631	0.654
scanline_42049	0.962	0.799	0.892	0.778
seatbelts	0.683	0.824	0.800	0.688
uk_coal_employ	0.868	0.966	0.920	0.928
unemployment_n1	0.876	0.843	0.669	0.628
usd_isk	1.000	0.814	0.737	0.863
us_population	0.785	0.615	0.853	0.787
well_log	0.832	0.495	0.793	0.679
Average	0.878	0.865	0.785	0.795

(a) Original results

dataset	alpha	beta	kappa	sequence	f1	covering
bank	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	1.000000	1.000000
brent_spot	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	0.597362	0.652154
businv	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	0.775510	0.695730
children_per_woman	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	0.809524	0.861270
co2_canada	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	0.679245	0.631299
construction	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	0.750000	0.679323
debt_ireland	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	0.958333	0.813624
gdp_argentina	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	0.888889	0.737087
gdp_croatia	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	1.000000	0.833333
gdp_iran	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	1.000000	0.813514
gdp_japan	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	1.000000	0.802140
global_co2	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	0.928571	0.758321
homeruns	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	0.878505	0.693803
jfk_passengers	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	0.965517	0.873088
lga_passengers	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	0.682607	0.595915
nile	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	1.000000	0.856800
ozone	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	1.000000	0.851852
quality_control_1	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	1.000000	0.988590
quality_control_2	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	1.000000	0.916770
quality_control_3	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	1.000000	0.996730
quality_control_4	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	0.780488	0.672741
quality_control_5	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	1.000000	1.000000
rail_lines	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	0.965517	0.871622
seatbelts	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	0.823529	0.688228
shanghai_license	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	0.965517	0.928166
uk_coal_employ	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	0.777293	0.555995
unemployment_n1	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	0.842604	0.627820
us_population	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	0.615385	0.786864
usd_isk	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	0.814229	0.862813
well_log	100.0	100.0	100.0	34	0.494759	0.678581

(b) Reproduction results

Figure 2: Comparison of the SB-BOCPD results

Comparison of the results As one can observe the results are the same, but just rounded to the 3 decimal digits. The test was performed with 29 datasets out of 36 (the ones that were tested in the original paper) in total. This gives us around 80% coverage of the original datasets (with the assumption that the unavailable datasets are 'randomly' unavailable) used and thus it is statistically not significant enough to state that we can expect the same result.

5 Findings, insights

In conclusion, despite conducting a thorough examination of the research paper’s reproducibility factors, including code verification, implementation, and result comparison, overall, the experiment does not attain a satisfactory level of reproducibility. While we successfully replicated the reported results by implementing the provided code, the absence of crucial information such as detailed environmental setup, comprehensive documentation, and clear instructions significantly hinders the credibility of the study. The lack of transparency in code dependencies, parameter settings, or experimental setup details introduces uncertainty and diminishes the overall confidence in the reproducibility of the research. Moreover, in the absence of all the essential information, our results also lack thorough explainability for the same reason. Therefore even though we have reached the same evaluation results as stated in the research paper, we cannot compare our success in terms of time, computational cost, or hardware resources. This example shows that to enhance the research’s validity and facilitate broader adoption within the scientific community, the authors should address these deficiencies by providing a more comprehensive account of their experimental methodology.

References

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